

Backward castes movement and political Participation in India

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Abstract

The political participation among backward classes. The origin of caste system, its impact on society and the various changes that the caste system has undergone over a period of time is critically looked at. The studies done by various scholars and the interpretation of the caste system by these scholars have also been dealt . The concept of political Participation and how the caste has taken a new form and is helping the traditional caste groups get politically mobilized and take active politics in the Democratic politics of the nation is also thoroughly analyzed along with the various social movements that are related to caste system in different parts of the country. Similarly, Review of Literature, the objective of the study, the hypotheses along with the methodology, Sample Design, Need of the study, Scope of the study, that is adopted for the sake of this study is also discussed.

Social Stratification is a ubiquitous social system in human societies, be it simple or complex. Stratification is fairly permanent ranking of positions in a society in terms of unequal power, prestige or privileges. It refers to the patterned or structured social inequalities among the whole categories people not just among individuals. The Caste system is the unique dimension, on which the Indian society is stratified into higher and lower castes with differential access to resources of society.

KEYWORDS: Social Stratification, Democratic Politics, Indian Society, Caste system, Upper Caste, Backward castes Leadership.

Caste System

In India, caste is the most important basis of social categorization. Initially caste originated on the basis of division of people on the basis of their natural inclinations and occupations and over a period of time it has turned out to be hereditary. It has created social groups based on kinship and ethnicity. The heredity occupations have created vested interests in the form of socio-economic monopolies and have bred an extreme form of exploitation. The main attribute of caste system is ritualistic purity, and this in turn has created inflexibility, rigidity and feelings of superiority and inferiority.

Basing on different perspectives there are various definitions of caste. How does one define caste? Although many social scientists have done epoch- making work on the Indian caste system, no two social scientists concur on its definition. They also differ on the meaning of caste. Some scholars hold the view that, caste is a particularly a rigid form of class and think its existence to be worldwide. Others believe it persists only in India and is peculiar to.

On the other hand, G.S.Ghurye, says that caste is strictly limited to the Hindus. He gives six outstanding features of the caste system: (1) segmental division of society (2) hierarchy (3) restrictions of feeling and social intercourse (4) civil and religious disparities and privileges of different sections (5) lack of unrestricted choice of occupation and (6) restrictions on marriage. He further says that the caste system is one of the oldest and the most elaborate systems of social organization. The position of an individual in the ritually determined hierarchy defines the entire course of his life.

The British historian H.H.Risley (1969) propounds a racist theory of caste. He argued that there were basic racial and physical differences among the various castes. This theory traces the origin of the caste system to the Aryan Invasion of India and links it to the process by which the invaders could subordinate the indigenous inhabitants and integrate them as peasants and slaves within a stratified society. This theory fails to explain the taboo on food and marriage. This view has been rejected by Indian intellectuals and politicians, including B.R.Ambedkar. Social reformers like Jyothirao phule and the leaders of the non-Brahmin movement in Tamil Nadlu also reject the Aryan theory, in which social superiority has been given to the Brahmin.

M.N.Srinivas, considers caste, as a cultural phenomenon. He refers to four features of caste (Brahmin, Kshatriya, Vysya, Sudhra) as embodied in Varna.

In one sense, all the castes which were considered upper in hierarchy in pre-British India were mainly urban and were sources of ritual and secular power or were close to these sources. Because of these initial advantages of higher status, the people belonging to these castes were the first to exploit the modern economic and educational opportunities that opened up during British rule, which the vast majority of the populace, who were mainly rural were deprived of these benefits. The latter remained backward in the traditional social order.

The Backward classes of contemporary India had their origin from the numerous artisan castes that were part of the societal schema of stratification, in which these castes were only just above the so called untouchables and their duty was to render services to the three higher castes in tune with the duties that were assigned to them as envisaged in the four Varna system.

The artisan castes though considered as backward were not treated as polluting as the untouchables because of their functional necessity for the agrarian society. They were allowed to reside in the vicinity of the village and their entry into the household was permitted when needed. But, both the Scheduled Castes and the Backward castes were socially set apart, excluded from power, education and rituals. In a nut shell, they were socially excluded, though they were rendering different essential services for the society.

J.H.Hutton as per a survey conducted during the British era came to a conclusion that there were about 3,000 castes existing in the country with relative degree of purity and pollution which were devoid of social, economic and political power and remained outside the social orbit and their efforts to attain social mobility was dissuaded and strongly discouraged by the higher castes.

On this basis, The Government of India gave a Commission Name by Mandal Commission; the Mandal Commission in the last decade of 20th century, identified 3743 castes to form India's other Backward classes, representing 52% of the country's population. Observing that the OBCs occupied only 12.5% of civil service posts, it recommended a 27% reservation for them in those posts. This figure was not proportional to their population. However, to be spared the ire of the judges, who, since the apex court upheld the decision, were

concerned with keeping quota totals below 50% (these 27% in fact were in addition to the 15% in favour of the Scheduled Castes and the 7.5% in favour of the Scheduled Tribes) recommended that figure.

OTHER BACKWARD CASTES POPULATION IN INDIA

The term “Backward class” makes a reference, to those backward groups which are discerned from Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. During the British regime they were addressed as the depressed classes. Similarly, some authors refer to backward classes as those classes which are far below the upper classes cluster, some others to those classes which are just above SCs and STs and some other writers refer to middle cluster of caste hierarchy as backwards. Different states of India, depending on their own criteria, have their own classification of Backward Classes in their respective states. The Census of 1951 and the Planning Commission of 1951 had estimated that OBC population constitutes nearly 20 percent of the total population. While the Kalelkar Commission (1953) was of the opinion that the total population of the OBCs in India was 31.8 percent, the Mandal Commission (1980) basing on its calculation came to a conclusion that OBC population constituted 52 percent of the population.

When Janata Government came to power in 1977, it appointed Mandal Commission, the Second Backward Classes to study and identify the backward castes in the population in the country. The Commission, submitting its report in 1980, identified 3743 backward castes. It also recommended 27 percent of reservations for OBCs in educational institutions as well as in Government services in both centre as well as in State Governments. Meanwhile the Janatha Government fell and the implementation of the Mandal Commission did not materialize and was gathering dust till the National Front Government under the aegis of V.P.Singh came to power in 1989.

The National Front Government in 1989 put into effect the recommendations of the Mandal Commission in 1990 and decided to grant 27 percent of reservations to the backward castes in educational institutions as well as in government service. This decision of the National Front Government was not taken kindly by the non- Backward classes population of the country, especially the forward castes and it resulted in nationwide upheaval. A total of 26 writ petitions were filed in different High Courts and in the Apex Court in Delhi. The apex court in its judgment in 1992, upheld the decision of the Government to grant 27 percent of reservations in educational institutions and in government jobs to Non- Creamy layer of OBCs. It was sequel to this that the National Commission for Backward Classes came into existence in 1992.

OBCs form 41% of population: Survey

In a fresh twist to the controversy over the proportion of OBCs to the overall population in India, a government survey which was released on September 1, 2007 indicated that the Backward Castes formed about 41% of the total populace. The OBC population in the country, according to a survey by the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) put it at 40.94%, while the population of SCs was put at 19.59%, and that of STs was put at 8.63% and the rest was put at 30.80%. The number is not really of great significance statistically because the NSSO survey was basically aimed at measuring the level of consumption expenditure by different households and not estimating the population of OBCs, SCs and STs,. In fact, a similar survey done in 1999-2000 had put the OBC population at about 35% and it is hardly likely that the proportion has gone up by 6% in just five years - the latest survey was done in 2004-05.

However, the new figure came to attain political significance because of the controversy which was centered around the OBC reservations in higher education and the Supreme Court's question to the Centre on how it had arrived at the 27% quota. The figure of 41% is much less when compared to the figure which was given by the Mandal Commission report and which happened to be 52%. The panel had arrived at the figure on the basis of the 1931 caste census by eliminating non-OBC communities from the total population.

According to a survey which was conducted to know the percentage of different social categories of people living in the rural areas, it came to be known that, 79.8% of SCs, 91.4% of STs, and 78.0% of OBCs were in rural areas. Conversely, 20.2% of SCs, 8.6% of STs, and 22% of OBCs were in urban areas, while 37.7% of 'others' lived in India's towns and cities.

When compared to the rural areas, the urban areas are spending on an average nearly twice the amount and the same is result of the booming economic growth. While the per capita monthly expenditure of people living in urban areas was Rs 1,052.36 a month and the per capita monthly expenditure of the rural areas is Rs 558.78. With minor exceptions, the general level of spending of SCs and STs was lower than OBCs and the others, while that of OBCs in turn was lower than that of the others.

According to the NSSO survey, the all India average spending by rural 'others' was Rs 685.31, followed by OBCs Rs 556.72, for SCs it was Rs 474.72, and the rural ST spending was the lowest at Rs 426.19. In urban India, while the STs spent Rs 857.46 on an average, the SCs spend Rs 758.38 on an average, the OBCs spend Rs 870.93 on an average and the others spend Rs 1,306.10 on an average, in a month. The survey highlights the fact that in rural India that a majority of 64.3% of the population depend on agriculture, and 39.4% make their living through self-employment in agriculture or as agricultural labor (24.9%). In this sector, the population dependent on self-employment (agriculture and non-agriculture) was reported to be 36.6% for SCs, 49.0% for STs, 60.7% for OBCs and 66.4% for others and that dependent on rural (agricultural or non-agricultural) labor was 56.4% for SCs, 45.2% for STs, 30.7% for OBCs and 21.8% for others.

In urban India, the proportion of population located in regular wage/salary earning households was almost the same (42.0% to 42.9%) for all social groups except OBCs (34.3%). Dependence on self-employment was more prevalent among OBCs (46.4%) as well as the residual class (45.3%) than the SCs (30.9%) and STs (27.4%).

EVOLUTION OF OBCs PARTICIPATION IN POLITICAL ACTIVITIES IN INDIA

Backward Castes movements have a long, chequered and uneven history of struggle against the dominant upper castes. The backward castes movement which began in South India in the 19th century became a major political force to be reckoned with by the first quarter of 20th century. In the northern states of Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and some other parts of North India, the backward classes' movement began in 20th century. However, The struggle of the Backward Classes took longer than its counterpart in South India to acquire sufficient political clout. A plethora of reasons could be cited for such low progress of the Backward Class movements in North India. Surprisingly, some states like Orissa, West Bengal, Madhya Pradesh and Assam haven't witnessed considerable movements of Backward Classes to this day. The movements both in the South India and North India were initiated and led by the upper strata of the Backward Classes, mainly the landed peasantry who had the awareness of the existing social, economic and political realities. The improved economic conditions of the Backward Classes due to the changes in agrarian structure, and/or penetration of

market economy and/or access to education enabled them to acquire the required social and political consciousness to fight for their dues in the existing social setup. Initially, that Backward Class leadership aspired for higher status in the caste hierarchy and achieved that. However, the rate of upward mobility for all the classes was not similar. The mobility of different castes varied from region to region.

The Backward Classes elite media demands for political positions both within the political parties as well as in the legislatures. This was true both in North as well as in South India. As a result, we would witness the Backward Class leaders manning positions in political parties as well as occupying seats and positions in State Assemblies, cabinet and public institutions. Later, they impressed upon the governments the need for extending reservations in government jobs and educational institutions to the youth of the backward classes. The enlightened and the upper state of different backward castes launched struggles separately for sanskritisation as well as for political positions on caste lines. Later they came together under the banner of backward castes and mobilized the lower backward castes for enlarged support in the political sphere. The first such organized movement, and arguably the most widespread one was launched by the non-Brahmins of the Madras Presidency.

Back ward Castes movement in Andhra Pradesh

The role played by the modern historical consciousness of region and language in the writing of caste historiography during the first half of the twentieth century has contributed to the creation of caste consciousness. It studies the Telugu-speaking Kammas, a dominant caste in Andhra, a region that has witnessed a vehement movement for linguistic states. Ever since the chaotic disputes on Andhra historiography flared up in 1910, ways to interpret the regional past have become crucial for their self-definition in the newly acquired idea of India as well as that of Hinduism with the whole debate ultimately leading to the emergence of some influential historiographies on the Kamma caste. Different historiographies from those of non-Brahmin leaders, Suriyadevara Raghavayya Chaudari and Tripuraneni Ramswami Chaudari, to the socialist cum nationalist leader, N.G. Ranga, and a caste movement ideologue, Kotta Bhavayya Chaudari demonstrates the correlation and complicity between history and caste identity and homeland language movements. They were, in a sense, on the lookout for a new, totally different history.

The role of caste become a preponderant thing in Andhra Pradesh because the state happens to be a highly caste conscious one. After the emergence of non-Brahmin movement with its own separate identity, two sub-castes, namely, the Reddys and Kammas began to play a more conscious and prominent role in Andhra Pradesh politics. Andhra Pradesh is one of the states where non- Brahmin Movement has changed the sphere of politics. Geographically, it has three regions, namely, Coastal Andhra, Telangana and Rayalaseema. The state of Andhra Pradesh though is backward economically, yet has contributed many political leaders for independence movement.

The Backward Class Movement in Tamil Nadu

The runaway lead taken by the Tamil Brahmins in the field of education in the erstwhile Madras Presidency has been well documented.²⁰ Tamil Brahmins and Vellalas happened to be the two dominant communities in the Madras Presidency. While the male literacy rate among the Tamil Brahmins was 73% the literacy rate of the Vellalas was 6.9% by the turn of the 20th century. Whereas the male literacy in English was only 0.19% among the Vellalas, it was 17.9% among the Tamil Brahmins. The Brahmins had become a force to be reckoned with in the Tamil Society and as a result established a near monopoly of the government services and the professions., The Madras Revenue Board, as far back as in 1851 had sternly instructed the District Collectors to restrict the number of the Brahmins who were entering into the government services. The Brahmins domination of the government services and the professions notwithstanding this instruction continued unabated. The caste's domination in the Provincial Congress Committee was quite manifest. The non-Brahmin elite castes, alerted by the advent of the Montague-Chelmsford reforms and diarchy, took the lead in establishing the first South Indian Liberal Federation, and later on the the justice Party in the year 1916. The Justice Party, after coming to power in 1920, extended the scope of the 1881 order, in 1921 and advised all the heads of the department not to recruit only Brahmins to the government posts but to distribute appointments of all the grades among the various communities and castes.

But for the first time in the history of the Madras Presidency, a clear cut reservation procedure, by the order of 1927, was laid down which provided compartmental reservations of posts for different categories.²¹ Many of the Brahmin leaders had also acknowledged they indeed had obtained a lion's share of the jobs and educational facilities and this had lead to a lot of heart burn among other communities. This necessitated the heralding of providing reservations to the communities other than Brahmins in the Presidency Till 1947, this scheme of reservation to the government jobs in the Presidency was in existence. The adversely affected Brahmins because of their numerical weakness could not offer any resistance to this scheme. The Brahmin youth of the presidency feeling stifled and squeezed by the operation of the 1927 order, started migrating to the other metropolitan cities of India, mostly Bombay. It can be seen from the G.O., that the Scheduled Castes who were earmarked only 8% of the jobs were also dissatisfied because the reservation that was provided to them was far less when compared to their share in the population. The first Congress ministry in Province headed by Rajaji, in spite of the infirmities, did not even touch the G.O in view of the strength of the non-Brahmin agitation and because of need to broaden the base of the Congress Party in the thirties by inducting more and more non-Brahmin elite into the party.²² The 1927 G.O. which was passed in the Madras Presidency represented a victory for the Vellala castes, particularly the Modaliars in the Tamil areas of Madras,. These people provided the leadership to the Justice Party, along with other non-Brahmn castes leaders. The Party leaders did not include the landless castes into their fold and broaden their base instead their leaders were drawn mostly from the landed classes.²³ The Justice Party, by the thirties, had served its historic purpose of reducing to a great extent the sense of deprivation on the part of the zamindar interests, particularly in the fields of government jobs and education. E. V. Ramaswamy Naicker in the meantime, walked out of the party in 1925 and started the self-respect movement because he was angered by the domination of the Brahmins in the Congress and he was also equally annoyed of Gandhiji's adherence to a purified varna ideology. Naicker

thought Brahminical religion and culture was the prime instrument of enslaving the Tamilians hence his movement aimed at nothing short of a rejection of it. Naicker by 1939, was demanding a separate Dravidistan. Like the Lingayat and Vokkaliga leaders in Karnataka by the end of the sixties, the elite non-Brahmins of Madras, but for the self-respect movement, would in course of time, would have been as isolated from the lower caste groups,

The Justice Party which was reconstituted as the Dravida Kazhagam, in 1944, was imbued with not only an anti-Hindi ideology, anti-North, anti-Brahmin, but also with separatist sub-nationalism. The Communal G.O. of 1927, in 1947, was revised. was historic because For the first time, according to the 1947 G.O. , the non-Brahmin castes were bifurcated into non-Brahmin Hindus and non-Brahmin backward Hindus. For obvious reasons , there was no resentment, due to this bifurcation, on the part of the non-Brahmin Hindus which consisted of the forward Naidu, Vellala, Reddy, Chettiyar, , etc., castes since they were given a compartmental reservation of 43% of the jobs.

The compartmental reservation, after the adoption of the Constitution, was struck down by the Supreme Court. Then the 1947 Communal G.O. was converted into 15% for Scheduled Castes, 7% for Scheduled Tribals, 25% for Backward Castes. The Madras Government, in the light of the population figures, after the separation of Andhra and of the Scheduled Castes and Tribes (after the 1951 census), promulgated in 1954 the following reservation scheme- Scheduled Castes and Tribes: 16%, open competition: 59%, backward classes 25%. The non-Brahmin forward castes who had two decades earlier provided the leadership to the non Brahmin movement, were now compelled to compete with Brahmins in the open competition pool. This did not give rise to any backward Castes from the non-Brahmin forward castes as they had become sufficiently powerful to hold on to their benefits in politics and as well as in services.²⁴ A defining feature of the above scheme was that it divided almost every major community or caste group in Tamil Nadu into forward and backward sections, Adi Saiva, Karghata, Kalaveli Vellalas are forward, and Thuluva Vellalas and Sozhi Vellalas are backward, Labbal and Deccan Muslims are backward, and Urdu-speaking Muslims are forward, Christian converts from the Scheduled Castes are backward, other Christians were forward; All Reddies are forward except Ganjam Reddys; Gavaru and Vadugar Naidus are backward; but Kamma Naidus are forward. Similarly, the Chettiyars are also divided into forward and backward sub-caste groups. This manner of division greatly reduced the potential of the forward sub-castes to protest or agitate.

In actual operation, it was the advanced castes among the notified backward classes who accrued the benefits of reservation The suggestion of the Tamil Nadu Backward Classes Commission to go for compartmental reservation for different categories of Other Backward Classes was not taken into consideration by the State Government. The conundrum, however was why did the weaker and minor backward castes which consisted of nearly 88.7% of the backward classes population did not express their resentment against the benefits of reservation being cornered by only a handful of castes? The answer lies in the peculiar Dravida Kazhagam culture which has been nurtured and fostered by both the DMK and the AIADMK. As long as the Tamil cultural revivalism continues to have grip over the State and as long as the anti-Hindu, anti-North and anti-Aryan issues dominate the minds of the people, a real backward classes movement espousing the cause of the really backward will not emerge. The same factors continue to provide cohesion between the various non-

Brahmin castes. The DMK leader particularly is not interested in anything which will weaken the ethos of the Tamil movement.

In Tamil Nadu, unlike in some other States, an open and enduring conflict between the OBC and the Harijans has not developed to eclipse the Brahmin vs non-Brahmin cleavage. Because Tamil Nadu with its non-Sanskritic cultural area did not lend itself to the four-fold varna system and did not appreciate its applicability there. The Harijans, as a result readily and promptly responded to Ramaswamy Naicker's Self-respect movement. These relationships, between the backward non-Brahmins and Harijans hence, neither threatened the forward non-Brahmins nor helped them. While the energetic Nadars could be able to improve their position to a great extent the others too did not feel much of a threat to their rank or status. The expanding Tamil Nadu economy did come to the help of those non-Brahmin forward castes which felt squeezed by the reservation schemes, Similarly, while the backward Brahmins have almost written off the Tamil Nadu government service the forward Naidu boys have begun going into industry, business etc⁽²⁶⁾. The Backward Class movement was not taken to its logical end of sustaining and expanding its base for eradicating the caste system, which if it were being taken to its logical conclusion would have destroyed not only the traditional status superiority of upper Backward caste over lower Backward castes in general but over the untouchable castes in particular. The cause of backward castes who are at the bottom of the hierarchy was always sidetracked because the leadership was consistent and concentrating in always raising the issue of imperialism of North Indian or Dravidians vs Aryans which.

The DMK leadership who had led the Tamil nationalism Movement in the 1950s, in the course of time "shifted its emphasis from that of race, to that of language which permitted an accommodation upward to include Tamil Brahmin". And the educationally backward castes of neighboring Mysore State also launched a parallel movement.

The Backward Classes Movement in Karnataka

Most parts of the present Karnataka State were parts of the earlier Mysore State. Mysore was handed back to the traditional rulers in 1881 after being in control of the British for nearly fifty years.²⁸ The important posts in the government came to be filled by Brahmins from Madras presidency both during the period of British rule and the later couple of decades. This has resulted in a lot of resentment and dissatisfaction on the part of Mysore Brahmins, who were particular about the Brahmins of Mysore getting the Government jobs and the Princely state and over a period of time stated gaining an upper hand and completely established their ascendancy.

While the Brahmins in the Princely Mysore State constituted a meager 3.8% of the population, Vokkalingas constituted nearly 20.4%, Lingayats constituted 12% and the percentage of the depressed classes was 15%. According to the 1901 Census, while 68% of the Mysore Brahmins were literate at the turn of the century, for Lingayats it was only 14.1% and for the Vokkaligas it was only 4% during the same period of time. The Brahmins of the Mysore State, like their counterparts in Madras Presidency, had established a runaway lead over the two dominant landed gentry's caste of the Vokkaligas and the Lingayats. While, the percentage of English knowing Vokkalingas rose from 0.7% to 1.09% and the percentage of the English knowing Lingayats increased from 0.13% to 2.34% during the next 40 years, the percentage of English knowing Brahmins increased stupendously from 10.2% to 36.2%. Almost contemporaneously with the

rise of the Justice Movement in Madras in the second decade of the century, the Lingayats and Vokkalingas of the Princely Mysore State became agitated over the Brahmins' preponderance in the government service and education. In the first decade of the century, their castes' associations appeared and by 1907 under the leadership of C.K. Reddy, Praja Mitra Mandali was established to voice the claims of the non-Brahmins.

A Committee, under the chairmanship of L.C. Miler (the Chief Justice of Mysore) was appointed by the Maharaja in 1918, on the basis of representations received from the aggrieved communities. The main mandate of the committee was "to consider the steps necessary for the adequate representation of non-Brahmin communities in public service". The government, after accepting the Miller report, passed orders in May 1921. The order, inter alia, constituted a Central Recruitment Board and reserved 75% of the vacancies for the backward classes.³¹ Meanwhile, the Praja Mitra Mandali, in the absence of a sharp focus got disintegrated and in turn its place was taken up by yet another party of non-Brahmins, Prajapaksha in 1928. The party consisted of younger elements of the two dominant castes who had considerable exposure to the caste conflicts in the neighboring States. The people of the Princely States were also being organized on parallel lines by the Indian National Congress to obtain democratic concessions. Many of the non-Brahmin stalwarts who were earlier aloof from the Congress Party were persuaded and compelled by the circumstances to join the Congress movement. In this way the Congress Movement in the State got intensified by the entry of the Lingayat and Vokkaliga landed gentry. After the merger of the Princely Mysore State into the Indian Union in 1947, while the Lingayat constituted their junior partners, the Vokkaligas started controlling the State apparatus as well as the Congress Party.

The caste equations got considerably altered after the formation of the unified Karnataka State in 1956. While the Vokkaligas constituted about 11% of the state's population, the Lingayats constituted 15%. The first Chief Ministers of the expanded Karnataka State were the Lingayats the community apart from dominating the rural country side through their hold over agriculture also controlled the sources of political patronage.

After the reorganization of the state, the new leaders extended the communal reservation scheme to the entire State and this has culminated in many litigations in the court of law like the famous Balaji judgment. The Government in 1963, later ordered 18% reservation for Scheduled Castes and Tribes and 30% reservation for the Other Backward Classes. The politically dominant castes of Lingayats and Vokkaligas were the main beneficiaries of this scheme. The other minority castes, who found themselves left high and dry due to this policy had nurtured considerable heart burn and resentment. Devraj Urs, who rose as the leader of the Congress (I), very carefully and assiduously cultivated the non-Lingayat and non-vokkaliga communities. It was primarily the consolidation of this base that enabled him to rule the State from 1972 to 1980.

Karnataka Backward Classes Commission which was headed by Mr L G Havanur was set up by Devaraj Urs in 1972. The Commission, after its thorough enquiry, did not include the Bunts, Brahmins, Khyatriyas, lingayats, and Jains in the list of Backward Classes. The Government divided the underprivileged classes into six categories and made separate reservation for each group after modifying the Commission's recommendations. The special feature of this scheme was that while it classified a majority of the sub-castes of the Lingayats as forward it classified only some sub-castes as backward. The Vokkaligas, however, have been classified as a backward community, their erstwhile senior partners in Karnataka politics, the Lingayats have been classified as mostly forward. The Lingayats, as a result, found themselves divided on the issue.

As a result of this policy, the Vokkaligas and the Lingayats found themselves in different camps of the backward and forward and an alliance between them could not take place. This was in sharp contrast to the situation in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar where all the major forward caste groups, i.e., Kayasthas, Brahmins, Bhumihars and Rajputs have been classified as forward and could find a platform to unite upon.

A considerable controversy between Lingayats and other backward classes was caused by the Havanur Commission Report. However protests and agitations organized by Lingayats did not cut much ice owing to effective mobilization of the smaller backward castes. Devraj Urs was very successful in forging the coalition of minority backward castes into a pretty powerful and durable entity. In the decades following the twenties, the Karnataka non-Brahmin movement was not successful in producing any overarching revivalist Kannada ideology which might have prevented the cleavage among the non-Brahmins from emerging to the surface. As discussed, the more recent cleavage has displaced the older Brahmin-non-Brahmin cleavage. The Lingayats, the Brahmins and Bunts of Karnataka like the Brahmins, Kayasths, Bhumihars and Rajputs of Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, have been kept out of the reservation scheme. The Karnataka Brahmins are so weak that even if they join hands with Lingayat, it would not make any difference. As the backward castes split between upper and lower backward castes, the Lingayats fought against each other to be included or excluded from backward caste lists in the 1970s.³⁴ In Karnataka, there was not much public agitation as long as the Lingayats had been classified as backward. The ire of the community was provoked when they were excluded from the list of the Backward classes on the basis of Havanur Commission initially and later by the G.O.s based on the report.

New castes begin to assert their claim with the dominant backward castes, as the competition among backward castes gets intensified and the backward castes get split, for the purpose of reservation, into backward communities and backward castes in Karnataka, non-Brahmin Hindu and backward Hindus in Tamil Nadu, and other backward classes and other backward classes in Bihar.

When the dominant stratum realizes that it is not possible for it to get reservation in the name of caste, they emphasize the economic criteria. Similarly, Lingayat and Vokkaliga communities having realized that they would not get backward status as caste, insisted that Chinnappa Reddy Commission (1990) should adopt economic criteria to identify the SEBs.

The non-Brahmin movement of Maharashtra, unlike the Backward Class movements of Tamil Nadu and Karnataka, took slightly different course and emerged at two levels: one led by the non-Brahmin Marathas and the other by the untouchable caste of Mahars. The organizational triumphs of these two large and effective protest movements in this century were dependent on the democratizing processes of the period of political reforms (1921-1939), but both had roots reaching back to an apolitical period in the last half of the Nineteenth century.

THE MAHARASHTRA BACKWARD CLASSES MOVEMENT

In South India, and in the Bombay Presidency particularly, from the second half of the nineteenth century, the sons local traders and moneylenders who expanded into Commerce and the sons of rich peasants among the dominant land-owning castes, started acquiring English education. A small fraction of this newly educated class also emanated from the lower Shudra artisan, cultivating, and trading castes, and some times even from among untouchables.³⁷ Maharashtra, Poona and Kolhapur, in the 19th century provide leadership and congenial ground to the emergence of backward castes movement in India. One of the first products of Christian missionary education was Jothiba Phule of Poona who hailed from the Shudra caste of gardener. Phule (1827-1890) is acknowledged and considered as the father of the first non-Brahmin movement in India. He was committed to the upliftment of the down trodden and wrote several books for the material and spiritual improvement of the lower classes. He was terribly moved by the condition of the untouchables. He called upon the people to revolt against the degrading religious practices and the Hindu casteist gods. He wanted the lower castes to form their own associations, create an spirit de corps and work for their emancipation from the age-old degradation as Shudras in society, education and religion.

With an intention to unite all the backward classes on a common platform, Jothiba founded the Satya Shodak Samaj. He strongly fought for the cause of adequate representation for members of all castes in public services without any exception.

The non-Brahmin movement which got initiated in Bombay Province (now Maharashtra) had its repercussions in Kolhapur – a small Maratha state which was under the control of Maharaja Chatrapati Shahu.³⁸ The Maharaja devoted much of his time to the non-Brahmin movement because he was displeased with the Brahmins. He declared that he would reserve at least half the posts in the State for qualified men of non-Brahmin communities in 1902. Kolhapur may be said to be the first state to adopt the reservation policy,. Kolhapur, as a result had proved, itself to be a landmark in the backward classes movement towards equality.³⁹ Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu have proved to be the home for Backward class movements. Gail Omvedt believes that Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu had the highest rural impoverishment and this in a way has produced a cultural revolt.⁴⁰ The organization and leadership to backward castes like Malis, Telis, Kumbis and Satis was provided by the Satya Shodhak Samaj. In subsequent years it prepared and provided the social base for the leadership of Bheemrao Ramji Ambedkar. The Government of Bombay, in 1928, set up a Committee headed by OHB started to identify backward classes and recommend special provisions for their advancement. The Committee, in the year 1930, in its report, classified backward classes into three categories, namely, aboriginal and hill tribes, depressed classes, and other backward classes and recommended the provision of special facilities regarding recruitment in government services and education to the above categories.

While the Depressed Classes Associations led by educated individual who represented untouchable communities could succeed ultimately in gaining reserved seats in the central Legislature and in provincial legislatures on a pan-Indian scale, the non-Brahmin movement had its maximum political impact in the Tamil region. Dr B R Ambedkar who happened to reject Gandhi's claim to personally represent all of India's untouchables and who was the foremost spokesman of the untouchables, was invited by the British to act as the delegate of the Depressed Classes at the Round Table Conference of 1930-32. The 1932 Poona Pact which

recognized untouchables as a political category across British India made provisions for giving reservations to the Depressed Classes in legislative bodies almost in proportion to their population. Dr Ambedkar made untiring efforts to kick start the process of an ideological awakening among the untouchables, especially the members of his Mahar Community. His succeeded in it and the result could be witnessed in gaining reserved seats for the Depressed Classes which provided a new political category with which they could identify.

The other backward classes of Maharashtra, also mobilized themselves as social groups. But the government policy was to move from caste to income criterion, the State Government appointed a Backward Classes Committee which was headed by B. D. Deshmukh in November 1961. The Committee submitted its report in January 1964. The Government, after broadly accepting the recommendations of the Committee made the following reservations in the educational institutions and in State services for Backward Classes: Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Caste converts to Buddhism 13%, Scheduled Tribes, Denotified Tribes and Nomadic Tribe: 4%; and Other Backward Communities: 10%. Thus the total percentage of reservations was 34%. The above scheme, interestingly, provided reservation, in proportion to population, only in the case of the first two categories. When it came to the case of the other backward communities the reservation that was provided was 10% of vacancies which were extended to all the Backward classes. The State Government, subsequently in April 1979, issued orders stating that 80% of all vacancies should be reserved for Economically Weaker Sections of Society, which effectively meant those families whose income was less than Rs200 per month. Where adequate numbers of suitably qualified candidates were not available from the families whose income was less than Rs200 per month, preference for the balance of reserved seats was to be given to candidates whose family income ranged between Rs200 and 400 per month. The 80% reservation that was given was inclusive of the earlier reservations that were made for the OBCs, SCs and STs.

ASCENDANCY OF BACKWARD CLASSES IN NORTH INDIA

The Backward classes' movements have varied in goals they were seeking, their support bases, the means they adopted, and the extent of relative deprivation. These variations to a great extent hinged on the impact of the British rule, the different type of cleavages that were provided by the inherited social structure, and the different public policies that were adopted and pursued by the post-Independence Governments, both in the States and at the Centre. Unlike in the peninsular India, the rise of the backward classes in North India, is basically a post-Independence phenomenon. The backward classes movement in the North India was the result of the conflict between the generally forward and "twice-born" castes of Brahmins, Kayasthas, Bhumihars, Rajputs on the one hand and the intermediate castes of Yadavs, Ahirs, Kurmis, etc, on the other. In South India, the backward classes movement had its origins in the Brahmin-non-Brahmin polarization. The closest approximation to the stratified social system of the varna order survived in the Ganges valley of its origin-a region which today accounts for 25% of India's population. The twice-born castes within this area are fully articulated and are represented by area-wide sub-castes of Brahmin, Kshatriya and Vaishya rank. As per the of 1931 Census which was conducted for the United Provinces, which is the most populous contemporary State of Uttar Pradesh, Brahmins constituted 9% of the population and Brahmins and Rajputs accounted for over 16% of the population, with Vaishyas (banias) adding another 2.5%. A similar varna order prevailed in

adjacent Bihar, where twice-born castes constituted more than 12% of the population and Kayasthas, accorded elite status as a *literati* caste, added a little more than 1%.

In the Hindi heartland areas, the varna divide between the twice-born castes and Shudras has been historically characterized by a rigid social hierarchy in which the lower castes were deprived of social dignity, denied education, and were confined only to manual work of cultivation on the lands of the upper castes or the other low status artisan and service occupations. Untouchables, by the very definition of the word, performed polluting tasks, and, in addition to that they had to work in the agriculture fields, commonly under the conditions of bonded labours. Brahminical ideology played the most important role in legitimizing the status and occupational hierarchy, although it was the Rajputs rather than Brahmins who exercised the greatest power as land controllers. High status groups (including ashraf Muslims) did not personally engage in cultivating the land, or in any sort of manual work which was left to jatis of the Shudras and to the untouchables.

The varna structure in South India, by itself could not give legitimacy to the secular stratification of wealth and power. The Brahmins who constituted only three to four percent of the population remained only at the apex of the ritual hierarchy and were unevenly distributed, and controlled extensive swathes of land only in some localities. The Kshatriyas, if present at all, were settled in extremely low concentrations. Vaishyas who were of indigenous origin were frequently outnumbered by immigrant Marwaris, Jains or other mercantile castes. In most of the South India, land-controlling groups came from origins which marked them as shudra by Brahminical criteria.⁴⁵ The impact of imperial power on dominance relations sanctified by the varna order, when compared to South India, was only somewhat more solid within the Aryan heartland of the Gangetic plain.

The Shudra category in North India could be categorically divided into two clearly identifiable sub-categories- and they are the lower Shudras and the upper Shudras. The former include the humble Hajjam, Kumbhar, Lohar, Teli, Tatwa, Dhanuk and Mallah and the latter consisted of such economically powerful and politically aggressive groups as the Jats, Yadavs, Kurmis and Koiris.⁴⁷ The Jats, though are not officially included in the backward classes list, they, however, regard themselves as the leaders of the backward classes. The inclusion of all these heterogeneous groups within the common Shudra category has enabled for its large size and has facilitated the leaders of the backward castes (that is the upper Shudras) to press hard for their claims as the champions of the depressed classes and for special status in the post-Independence period. Their contention was that the Congress Party (via the Nehru model of development which served as its ideological framework) was instrumental in empowering only a small group of upper castes, a pro-industry group, at the expense of the rural majority. This, they claimed, has left the backward castes with no choice but to launch an all out attack not only on the Congress system but also on all that it stands for. They further said that the upper caste dominance in the Congress party has been well documented.⁴⁸ The leaders of these Backward classes did not take into cognizance of the fact that the Congress party was also instrumental in bringing about a veritable revolution in the countryside through its land reform legislations and it was the land reforms that was primarily responsible for dispossessing the big zamindars and empowering the backward castes by assigning them lands. The reforms led to the creation of a substantial class of medium-sized owner-

cultivators, many of whom belonged to the backward classes. “Self-employed cultivators are largely a product of post-Independence agrarian policies, unlike the large landowners whose origins and resources are located in the history of the British Raj. As a consequence, the center of power shifted from the feudal landlords to the market-oriented independent cultivators”.

The principal losers in Northern India, in caste terms, were Rajput-Thakurs and to a lesser extent Kayastha, Bania, and Muslim landlords. The main beneficiaries of the changes that were heralded in were the erstwhile tenants among Yadavs, Jats, Koiris, Kurmis, who were belonging to the upper strata of the Shudra castes. These groups, after cornering the benefits of this first wave of agrarian legislation, took the lead in blocking all subsequent attempts at reforms which were designed to benefit the marginal farmers and the other landless classes who usually belonged to groups and castes further down the hierarchy. “Bullock capitalists” (as middle peasants are referred to by Rudolph and Rudolph), middle peasants, Independent agricultural producers, backward classes, intermediate castes, backward castes are all overlapping terms. All these generally refer primarily to those members of the Shudra castes who are self-employed, use a pair of bullocks, operate holdings between 2.5 to 15 acres, and the new inputs associated with the green revolution.

The principal backward castes in the premier state of the Hindu heartland Uttar Pradesh, namely, the Yadavs, Lodhas, Kurmis and Gudjjars, in the pre-Independence period, controlled 6% of the zaminadari rights in the State. However, 20% of the land came to be owned by these four castes (together they comprise 15% of the state’s population) after independence. If we take all the backward castes of U.P. we can understand that their share of Zaminadar rights which was only 8% prior to independence acquired control over 38% of the land after Independence.⁵¹ The displacement of large landowners by middle farmers happens to be one of the most significant and striking developments of the post-Independence period. Today the middle farmers constitutes one of the most powerful group in the countryside politically as well as economically. They have more voters than any other agrarian class taken itself – about 25% of the total population –and have emerged as the principal spokesmen of agrarian interest. But agrarian interests for them remain confined to the interests of middle farmer which explains why their major demands have been remunerative prices and other inputs costs—and lately, administrative jobs via the Mandal Commission. Politically, the single most important cause of the decline of the Congress in North India is the rise of the middle farmer. The congress party, despite its electoral dependence on the Scheduled Castes, forward castes, Scheduled tribes and minorities till 1967, was also successful to a great extent in incorporating sections of the backward castes even though they did not serve as its “vote bank”. To quote an instance, until he quit the party in 1967, Charan Singh remained an important leader and the preeminent spokesman of rural interests in the Congress Party.

The challenge of the middle peasants, for the first time, emerged clearly in 1967, when the Congress Party lost power in all North Indian States at the State level and middle peasants took over as chief ministers in Uttar Pradesh (Chaudhury Charan Singh), Haryana (Rao Birendra Singh), Bihar (B.P.Mandal) and Madhya Pradesh (G.N.Singh). One must turn to the States of Uttar Pradesh and Bihar to have a still clearer picture of the increasing political clout of the backward castes.

PROMINENT OBC REPRESENTATIVES IN INDIAN POLITICS

In spite of the low political representation of Backward Castes in Indian politics, it must be noted that some Backward Castes leaders have occupied an important place in Indian politics today. Sri Narendra Modi as leader of BJP, Akhilesh Yadav, Mulayam Singh Yadav as leaders of Samajwadi Party and Nitish Kumar as leader of (BSP), Lalu Prasad Yadav as Leader of RJD, Siddaramaiah as leader of Congress in Karnataka State, Muthuvel Karunanidhi as leader of DMK, Panneerselvam as leader of AIDMK H. D. Kumaraswamy as leader of Jantha Party are instances in point. Deva Gowda, Bandaru Dattatreya, Uma Bharti, Devaragunda Venkappa Sadananda Gowda, Ch. Birender Singh, Sanwar Lal Jat, Krishan Pal Gurjar, Sanjeev Balyan, Gowdara Mallikarjunappa Siddeshwara, Raosaheb Dadarao Patil Danve, Mansukhbhai Dhanjibhai Vasava, Sharad Yadav, Rabri Devi, Ryaga Krishnaiah, Chintakayala Ayyanna Patrudu, Pithani Satyanarayana, Butta Renuka, Kristappa Nimmala, Rammohan Naidu, Kinjarapu Konakalla Narayana Rao, Kambalapadu Ediga Krishnamurthy Gouda. Some of them head important and strong regional political parties which have been in alliance with major national political parties both outside and within national government. Even though the rise of some of these Backward Castes leaders might be linked to their proximity to big party leaders, they now hold a position of leadership within the party in their own right and can influence the decisions of their own party as well as the course of national politics.

Political leadership by Backward Castes is not dramatically different from that of upper caste. Backward Castes leaders are no better or worse than upper caste. They are as power driven as their upper castes peers. Backward Castes leaders have not been typically anxious to give greater representation to other Backward Castes within their own organizations or in the political process generally. Representation of Backward Castes has not necessarily increased greatly under the leadership of Backward Castes. In fact, interestingly, it is the 73rd Constitutional amendment and the policy and implementation of (Within State Concerned) 34% reservation for Backward Castes in Panchayats within State concerned which has enabled a lot of backward class leaders to take an active role in the local bodies' elections.

Thus the Indian political system cannot be said to be non respectful to the emergence and dominance of Backward Castes leaders even though the political representation of Backward Castes has not particularly registered a significant increase over the last 16 general elections. While on the one hand most Backward Castes politicians have found it difficult to rise within upper castes dominated party hierarchies, on the other hand some Backward Castes have managed to become leaders when they have set up parties of their own. Once they have established themselves as leaders, there has been an unquestioning acceptance of their leadership and decisions by the party rank and file, even if it is largely upper caste.

Backward Castes in Parliament or legislatures do not necessarily confine themselves to their issues only. In the absence of a specific mandate for representing Backward Castes issues, most of them feel that they represent both Backward Castes and upper castes of their constituencies. Like upper caste, they are drawn into the game of power with all its ruthlessness even though Backward Castes people approach to politics may not be identical to that upper castes. In fact even the Backward Castes wings or organizations of parties are not necessarily marked by kind of Backward Castes perspective or sensitivity. Also, the Varna articulations whether by upper caste politicians and leaders are internalized by Backward Castes candidates in presenting

themselves as ‘Bahujans’ and ‘betas’ relying on traditional Varna notions of Depressed Class are not absent in Indian politics. Many times Backward Castes public figures do adapt to and adopt upper castes priorities predominating in public life in order to be acceptable. Many Backward Castes leaders internalize the norms and roles of Vernacular political structures and merely replicate them instead of questioning them, resulting in reinforcing existing hierarchies of power.

Questions have been raised as to whether an increase in numerical strength of Backward Castes in the political process and decision making bodies automatically lead to a qualitative shift in power and whether Backward Castes on balance pay greater attention to the concerns of Backward Castes more than upper castes politicians. Problems of tokenism, visibility, marginality etc. are often discussed in referring to Backward Castes as a ‘minority’ operating in an upper castes’ domain.

Backward Castes rights and responsibilities to participate equally in political life should not however be treated as a ‘minority’ issue. The political space must belong to all citizens – Backward Castes and Upper castes. There is no doubt that fewer the Backward Castes leaders in public life, the lesser the likelihood of distinctively Backward Castes values, priorities and characteristics finding expression. Hence Backward Castes involvement in political process and decision making in greater numbers can make a significant difference.

Does that mean that only people similar to a group can represent its interests? This may not necessarily be true. In this context it is important to examine what interests Backward Castes in the public/political sphere are furthering. It could be argued that issues important to Backward Castes could be reasonably represented as well by Upper castes Members of Parliament. But many strongly feel that without a sufficient Backward Castes presence in the national and other decision making bodies, it seems unlikely that issues which Backward Castes as a group are more prone to be faced with – challenging other inequalities within the social and economic sphere – would be adequately addressed.

While it is considered important to bring Backward Castes to positions of power, it is equally necessary to sensitize those in power whether upper castes or Backward Castes. Along with this the importance of Backward Castes economic independence, education and awareness and their improvement in the socio-economic sphere can hardly be stressed. The restructuring of Castes relations within both the family and society is an equally important step towards freedom, equality and justice.

Table – 1.1

Caste –wise List of Indian Presidents during the period 1950- 2016

Number of Presidents	OC	OBC	SC	ST	Muslim	Christian	Sikhs
15	09	0	1	0	4	0	1

Source: Election Commission of India.

Table – 1.2

Caste – wise list of Prime Ministers of India

Number of Prime ministers	OC	OBC	SC	ST	Muslim	Christian	Sikh	Total
15	12	3	0	0	0	0	1	3

Source: Election Commission of India.

We can infer from the above table the number of OBC candidates who had served as Ministers in the Union Council of Ministers at the Centre. In the Ministries that were formed at the Centre in 1947, 1952, 1957, 1962, 1964, 1966, 1967, 1971 there was only one candidate from the OBC community who acted as Minister in the Union Council of Ministers out of the total strength of 16, 15, 13, 16, 16, 15, 19 and 13 in the Union Council of Ministers respectively. In the years 1977, 1979, 1980, 1984, 1989 there were only 3, 4, 2, 1, 6 OBC candidates from among 20, 19, 15, 14, and 18 Ministers in the Union Council of Ministers respectively. Likewise in the years 1990, 1991, 1996, 1997 there were only 1, 7, 11, and 14 OBC candidates from among the 11, 22, 24, and 31 Ministers in the Union Council of Ministers. Similarly in the years 1999, 2004, 2009, and 2014 there were 16, 23, 21, and 16 OBC candidates who acted as ministers among 57, 79, 77, and 66 Ministers in the Union Council of Ministers respectively. Thus, we can understand that the number of Ministers in the Union Council of Ministries is not commensurate with the population of the BCs in the country

Table – 1.4

List of Speakers

Number of Lok Sabha Speakers	OC	OBC	SC	ST	Muslim	Sikkah
13	10	0	2	1	0	0

Source: Election Commission of India.⁵⁶

We can gather from the above table that Lok Sabha had 13 Speakers till date. Among them 10 Speakers belonged to the OC category and 2 belong to the Scheduled Caste category and 1 belonged to the Schedule Tribe category. To this day not even a single OBC category candidate has acted as the Speaker of Lok Sabha.

He is of the opinion that we should try to improve representative practices and forms to make them more open, effective, and fair, rather than opposing participation to representation.

It is evident from the above review that most of these studies are broadly focusing on the overall political process in the country rather than social mobilization of the backward castes.

Objectives of the Study

Keeping the study gaps in the earlier studies and need for the study in mind, the following issues are considered as main objectives of the study. To analyse the concept of the Backward Castes system and the Politics of Backward Caste from historical perspectives and theories of representations for understanding the political participation and the representation patterns.

Methodology

The present study is based on both primary and secondary sources keeping in view the objectives of the research study. The primary data was collecting through the records. Most of the information is secured through administering. The secondary data is collected from the Gazettee records of Government of India Reports of various studies and also from various books and journals pertaining to Backward Castes representation. Data is also collected from various national and regional news papers.

Hypothesis

1. There has been growing political awareness among the backward castes.

Scope of the Study

An attempt is made in this thesis to study the concept of Backward Castes rises and Political Participation in India.

Need and Importance of study

selected for the purpose of studying the Back ward Caste political leadership.

it is interesting to study the position and participation belonging to Backward Castes in the Indian politics.

The Backward Caste population in the India, with its 46.1% share in the population largely resembles that of india 's Backward Caste population. Thus, it does not differ very much from the India in respect of demographic figures and the selection is very much relevant for the same appearance as the caste composition and population.

Analysis of data

In the present study various statistical methods and tools such as comparative percentage, diagrams used to analyse the available data.

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